

Developing Coping Skills in Engineering Students to Overcome Emotional Challenges: A Participatory Approach from Project-Based Learning

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Abstract

The project aims to enhance resilience and coping skills in university students to overcome emotional challenges by employing the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach with a focus on Participatory Action Research (PAR). This paper exclusively addresses the design of the pedagogical intervention. The target population comprises students admitted to the Systems and Computing Engineering and Industrial Engineering programs through special admissions at the Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Faculty of Engineering, in Bogotá D.C. and Cundinamarca. This group has an increasing prevalence of emotional problems among young university students, attributed to specific socioeconomic and cultural factors. The project is structured around a comprehensive and participatory methodological process, engaging youth in problem identification, solution design, intervention implementation, and results evaluation. Active youth participation is prioritized across all project stages, fostering empowerment and commitment. The methodology includes phases such as problem identification and definition, intervention planning, implementation, evaluation and reflection, adjustments and improvements, results consolidation, dissemination and socialization of learning, empowerment and continuity, and continuous monitoring. A multidisciplinary team collaborates with young individuals throughout each project phase. Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO) include the clear identification of emotional challenges, the design and implementation of effective interventions, bolstering resilience and coping skills, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of initiatives. Emphasis is placed on sharing learnings and results within the university community to promote replicability and the proliferation of best practices. This project addresses the emotional health issues in university students by providing practical tools and strategies to confront and overcome emotional challenges, thereby fostering their well-being and holistic development. Its participatory and collaborative approach positions it as a significant contribution to active learning and mental health promotion in university contexts.

Keywords: Project Based Learning (PBL); Engineering Education; resilience and coping skills; Participatory Action Research (PAR).

1 Introduction

This project aims to promote coping skills in young students who enter through the special mobility admission program (Special Admission Students) of the National University of Colombia, specifically in the undergraduate programs of Systems and Computing Engineering and Industrial Engineering at the Bogotá campus. The goal is to help these students overcome emotional challenges through an educational intervention supported by the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach and Participatory Action Research (PAR).

The project addresses the persistent and growing challenge of emotional health, characterized by a significant increase in the incidence of emotional health problems such as anxiety, depression, stress, and feelings of hopelessness. Additionally, it seeks to tackle the lack of in-depth training programs to promote the necessary skills for students to confront their emotional challenges effectively. Without such training, students may be inclined towards negative coping strategies, such as the consumption of psychoactive substances and engagement in risky behaviors. During adolescence, a crucial phase in individual development marked by significant biological, psychological, and social transformations, coping skills —or coping strategies— that

integrate methods and techniques to handle stressful situations, emotional problems, or life challenges acquire special relevance (Frydenberg, 1997).

The Lazarus and Folkman model (1984) highlights, in the understanding of coping, how the changing efforts to manage excessive demands distinguish between problem-focused and emotion-focused coping. It also identifies different categorizations (Crespo and Cruzado, 1997). Frydenberg and Lewis (1996b) define three styles of coping: productive, non-productive, and other-oriented.

Studies point out gender differences in coping strategies. For example, women are more prone to non-productive strategies, while men are more likely to ignore problems (Frydenberg and Lewis, 1994, 2000; Hampel and Petermann, 2005; González et al., 2002). These aspects are compiled in a study that relates coping to the personal well-being of students, concluding that coping strategies focused on the positive are associated with greater personal well-being (Viñas et al., 2015).

Two coping strategies have been selected to be implemented in the pedagogical intervention: Self-Instruction Training and Stress Inoculation Training.

Self-Instruction Training

Self-instruction training is a metacognitive coping strategy that involves thinking about our thoughts, actions, and behaviors. It focuses on learning to give ourselves instructions to regulate our behavior. This strategy was proposed by Meichenbaum in the 1940s. Deficits that occur when a problem arises can be due to issues in understanding, production, or mediation. In this workshop, it is considered relevant to address the concept of self-regulation, which can be learned through the following phases:

- Adult cognitive modeling.
- Participant cognitive modeling.
- Self-instructions.
- The fading of aloud instruction.
- Internal self-instructions.

Likewise, the functions to be executed are preparing to face the situation, focusing attention on the task, guiding behavior, providing reinforcement, evaluating the results, and reducing anxiety.

The procedure includes seven stages:

- Carry out self-records: Evaluate how the student is performing the activity, maintain useful actions, and reduce non-useful actions.
- Generalize good actions: Ensure that self-instructions lead to the generalization of good actions.
- Identify situations and components: Recognize situations and components according to the context.
- Focus attention on the problem: Answer the questions: What should be done? and, how should it be done?
- Define specific rules: Be attentive to different response possibilities or alternative solutions.
- Handle errors: Identify failures, their causes, and their consequences.
- Self-reinforcement: Identify the efforts made and the results achieved.

Stress Inoculation Training

Stress Inoculation is akin to a vaccine; its purpose is to improve coping responses in low-intensity situations to prepare individuals for high-intensity situations. It is based on the following models: the Transactional Stress Model (Lazarus and Folkman, 1984) and the Reciprocal Determinism Model (Bandura, 1977), where external environmental demands are high, and individuals cannot respond with the resources they have. Additionally, it incorporates models of cognitive-affective processes, where the origin of stress is influenced by various interrelated elements, such as cognitive, affective, physiological, behavioral, and environmental factors, as well as traumatic or stressful events that can invalidate fundamental beliefs about the world or the meaning of life.

This training integrates a series of techniques to address four types of stress:

- Acute time-limited stressors: These include students who develop anxiety related to specific events, such as giving public presentations, taking exams, or completing classwork.
- Sequential stressors: This occurs when a series of events are chained together, such as economic situations preventing a student from traveling to the university, leading to missed classes, poor nutrition, health problems, loss of concentration and attention in academic aspects, poor evaluations and assessments, and eventually, the loss of the subject and the semester.
- Chronic intermittent stressors: This affects individuals with recurring diseases who must retake tests on fixed dates over periods of years and months to determine their health status.
- Continuous chronic stressors: This includes exposure to one or more difficult situations for many years, such as chronic pain that persists continuously without a cure.

The purpose of this type of training is to change disturbing imaginations, images, and self-verbalizations through self-regulation, replacing them with functional imaginations, images, and self-verbalizations. Additionally, it aims to change maladaptive behaviours to adaptive ones and replace negative cognitive structures with alternative ones. These objectives are achieved through three phases: Conceptualization, Skill Acquisition and Training, and Skill Application, which are described below.

Conceptualization: involves evaluating and training self-observation. This phase includes defining problems in concrete, specific, non-evaluative behavioral terms. Each problem must be defined independently and separately, with an exhaustive search for internal and external variables that have created and maintained the problem. It also involves identifying coping difficulties and potential deficits in specific skills or cognitive/behavioral/emotional interferences. The reconceptualization of the problem should be manageable and credible for the student, distinguishing changeable stressors from unchangeable ones, and dispelling beliefs and myths related to emotional responses and reactions to stress.

Acquisition and training of skills: This integrates the following elements.

- Imagination or live exposure techniques: Used for phobias, fear, and avoidance.
- Modeling or Graduated Exposure: Gradual exposure to challenging situations.
- Operant Techniques: Behavioral reinforcement strategies.
- Problem-solving: Breaking down situations into manageable units and developing action plans.

The steps involved

- Situation to resolve, analysis of requirements to solve the situation, divide the situation into units, and prepare the action plan.
- Self-reinforcement training is carried out using cognitive Self-Instruction, this is when disconfirming evidence is considered.
- Self-Instruction to confront the stressor (preparation: focus on what needs to be done and not confront the stressor. In this case, self-instruction is used to control the stress reaction, perform a non-catastrophic interpretation, reinforce the trained skills, and then the coping with the discomfort).
- Self-Instruction guides to stay in the situation, and assessment of efforts, this implies Self-Instruction to evaluate what has worked, progress, and self-recognition). It is important to know the different strategies such as:
 - Strategies to Control Emotional Activation such as (Relaxation, deep breathing, and detecting moments before activation to use them in moments of tension).
 - Behavioral strategies (Imagination or vivid exposure techniques: when you have a phobia, fear, avoidance; Modeling, Graduated exposure; operant techniques; problem solving: Moments of pain pass, it occurs at different times; train habits and behaviors.
 - Palliative Coping Strategies. To mitigate discomfort in unavoidable or difficult-to-control situations. Perspective Taking: when there is a feeling of helplessness, focus on the changes that are occurring, through contact with people in a similar situation.

Application: This phase has the following aims: putting the learned strategies into practice in real situations, checking their usefulness and effectiveness, and addressing problems that arise during implementation. To promote the application of coping strategies, self-instructions must be prepared for various moments, gradual exposure to different situations should be carried out from positive to negative, graduation with exposure in

imagination or role-play should be implemented, coping strategies should be used to prevent relapses during high-risk moments for cognitive, emotional, or behavioral reactions, and attributions of self-efficacy should be promoted and reinforced. Finally, coping efforts and success, whether total or partial, should be assessed. For maintenance and generalization, generalization should be gradually worked on, encouraging the student to face different real situations and spacing out sessions to focus only on maintenance sessions. Other relevant aspects should also be included in maintenance, and students should be encouraged to train others in similar circumstances to solidify their learning.

Considering that the Participatory Action Research (PAR) approach is used to comprehensively address this problem in a participatory manner, involving students in identifying solutions, implementing effective strategies, and continuously evaluating to improve the emotional and life health of the student population in the university context. The research question posed is as follows: *How can an educational intervention be designed to promote coping skills among students in the (Special Admission Students) program of the Faculty of Engineering at the National University, aimed at addressing emotional challenges and supported by Participatory Action Research (PAR) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach?*

Concerning the methodology, research is mixed, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative methods. The research type is descriptive and quasi-experimental, without a control group or random selection. The project will be executed through a participatory-collaborative action research process, with students actively participating in defining coping problems, designing solutions, evaluating results, and incorporating didactic and pedagogical strategies to strengthen coping skills.

2 Scope

Emotional health problems have a significant impact on students' quality of life, affecting their interpersonal relationships, academic performance, and ability to achieve their potential. It is important to highlight that activities promoting soft skills are included in students' academic training programs. In the Faculty of Engineering at the National University of Colombia, training programs for skills development have been provided. However, teaching and learning activities specifically aimed at effectively addressing emotional challenges have not been incorporated, potentially leading to the adoption of negative coping strategies. Therefore, there is a clear need to designed effective educational interventions. Consequently, the objective is to design an educational intervention that promotes coping skills among students in the Special Admission Students program of the Faculty of Engineering at the National University, addressing emotional challenges through a combination of Participatory Action Research (PAR) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL).

2.1 Methodological Design of Educational Intervention

2.1.1 Aims

Below are the general and specific aims intended to be achieved through the educational intervention: To promote coping skills among (Special Admission Students) enrolled in the undergraduate programs of Systems and Computing Engineering and Industrial Engineering at the Bogotá Campus of Universidad Nacional de Colombia, helping them overcome the emotional challenges they face through an educational intervention supported by the Problem-Based Learning approach and Participatory Action Research.

Specifics

- To identify the emotional challenges and the coping mechanisms characteristic of special admission students by implementing standardized tests designed for this purpose.

- To plan the educational intervention, which includes defining specific objectives for the strategies and activities to be undertaken by special admission students, outlining strategies for enhancing coping skills, and creating a detailed action plan.
- To implement the strategies and activities within the framework of the Educational Intervention following the stages defined during its planning.
- To evaluate the educational intervention by integrating feedback from students using defined metrics, leading to the formulation of improvements in the intervention. This step aims to continuously adapt the intervention to achieve effective results.
- To reflect on the effect of the intervention on the quality of life of special admission students, supporting argumentation and interpretation of the results and information, as well as observing changes in behavior and engaging in joint reflection on what works and what needs to be adjusted.

2.1.2 Intervention Protocol

The intervention protocol described below includes the actions and procedures to be carried out to meet the aim, the strategies, the methods and tools to be used, the steps to be followed in each stage of the intervention, the procedures for collecting and analyzing data, and the criteria for evaluation and progress monitoring. This is done to ensure consistency, quality, and effectiveness of the intervention, as well as to facilitate replicability and comparison of results in similar studies. In response to the research question, the intervention protocol incorporated in the methodological design are described in detail below. Actions and products associated with each of the aims are presented in the following Table 1.

Table 1. Intervention Protocol.

Aim	Actions	Products	Week
1	• Perform the Coping tests (Frydenberg and Lewis 1996b).	• Document summarizing challenges and characterization of the type of coping used in students before the educational intervention.	1
2	• Design Workshops, training sessions, group activities to strengthen coping skills.	• Action plan with objectives and strategies. Record of Intervention Sessions. Educational Didactic Material (Workshops, support documents for training, rubrics for assessment and evaluation of activities)	2
3	• Train students in activities that facilitate the strengthening of coping skills in a sustainable way. • Implement the workshops using the educational teaching material that was designed in the intervention planning stage.	• Record of training activities.	3
4	• Consolidate the results in easily accessible digital media, so that they can be transferable to other students; These digital media include educational materials and sustainable strategies to disseminate the benefits obtained. • Disseminate the learning that was the result of the special admission students participatory action research with the university community. • Establish a continuous monitoring system to evaluate the short-term effectiveness of the educational intervention and adjust as necessary.	• Training activity plan. • Document of good practices and lessons learned. • Dissemination report and presentations. • Continuous monitoring report.	4
5	• Analysis of the Results. • Joint reflection on what worked or what needs to be adjusted.	• Report on opportunities for improvement and results of joint reflections.	5

2.1.2.1 Definition of Strategies (E), Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO) and procedures for data analysis (PDA)

Three strategies were developed as part of the educational intervention. These strategies and procedures are grounded in psychological principles related to metacognitive learning, emotional self-regulation, reflection, critical analysis, and decision-making, all of which are fundamental aspects in the development of coping skills among engineering students. Tables 2 to 4 provide details on the name of each strategy, the instruments to be used, the Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs), and the procedures for data analysis. The strategies are designed to help Engineering students at the Universidad Nacional de Colombia manage emotions within the university academic context. These strategies objectives to prepare students to successfully navigate academic situations that elicit various emotions, such as delivering oral presentations of their research to the community and engaging in problem-solving activities.

Table 2. Holistic approach for activating coping skills in engineering students' strategy.

Strategy/Instrument Denomination: Holistic approach for activating coping skills in engineering students" / Coping Scales Test .		
At the end of the strategy, students will be able to	Teaching Activities TA/Learning Activities LA /Evaluation Activities EA	Procedures for Data Analysis - PDA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify specific coping strategies. Distinguish specific and general coping, allowing for a differentiated understanding of how they deal with situations versus how they deal with various situations in their daily lives. 	<p>TA: Preparation of the presentation and documentation of the types of coping and the ACS explanation of the test to be used in the students.</p> <p>LA: Participation at the end of the presentation with questions about any doubts that may arise regarding the presentation of the ACS test.</p> <p>EA: Presentation of the ACS test by the student.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of the specific coping strategies used by students between 16 and 17 years of age, through the analysis of the responses (ACS) of Frydenberg and Lewis (1996b) and analysis of the ACS subscales to understand the diversity of strategies coping strategies available, from approaches focused on problem solving to those focused on emotional regulation. Evaluation of the effectiveness and frequency with which different coping strategies are used, detection of adolescents' preferences and abilities to face challenges. Integration of ACS test results with other assessments and observations to obtain a holistic view of coping skills.

Table 3. Self-instruction training for anxiety management in solving problems strategy.

Strategy/Instrument Denomination: "Self-instruction training for anxiety management in solving problems"/ Workshop 1 - ASC, Self-assessment Rubric, Knowledge Test, Semi-structured interview.		
At the end of the strategy, students will be able to	Teaching Activities TA/Learning Activities/Evaluation Activities	PDA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-record their actions and thoughts while trying to solve a programming problem. Identify which actions and Self-instructions are effective and can be applied to different problems. Analyze the context of the problem to determine what actions are necessary. Establish rules that answer fundamental questions about what to do and how to do it in the context of the problem. Identify errors, their causes, and consequences to learn from them. Apply Self-Reinforcement in your efforts and results in solving the problem. 	<p>Activity 1.</p> <p>TA: Activity Design</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adult cognitive modeling, which will be used to address the situation that the student faces when solving a specific engineering problem in the Computer Programming subject where he cannot understand the procedure statement, or he understands what the statement says but He does not know how to provide a solution, or he recognizes that he must apply techniques and procedures but he does not know which of them is appropriate and he does not know how to provide himself with the appropriate instructions for the technique or procedure that will adequately guide him to the solution. Participant cognitive modeling: in which the same previous situation is addressed, but an algorithm is if leads to the solution of the problem, the teacher points out each step and the student executes it until reaching the solution. Self-instructions: The student is given the same problem to solve where the variables and conditions are different, the algorithm that corresponds to the sequences of instructions leads to the solution, but in this case the student executes the instructions out loud. The Fading of the instruction out loud: When the sequence of instructions is performed mentally and leads to the solution. Internal self-instructions: When the student executes the sequence of solutions that leads to overcoming the problem through internal thought processing, where each step is indicated. <p>LA: The student develops the steps established in the Self-instruction training.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Self-Assessment Rubrics: Which evaluates the student's performance in terms of emotional self-regulation, reflection, analysis, and decision making. Knowledge Test in the application of sorting algorithm. Reflective interviews integrate open questions so that participants reflect on their experiences, perceptions, thoughts, and emotions. In the context of coping and self-regulation, interviews can explore the strategies used to face challenges, the perception of the effectiveness of these strategies, and the learnings obtained.

Table 4. Activate the ability to cope with anxiety situations in the academic environment strategy,

Strategy/Instrument Denomination : Activate the ability to cope with anxiety situations in the academic environment / Workshop 2 -includes Knowledge Test, Semi-structured Interview and Feedback Questionnaire		
At the end of the strategy, students will be able to	Teaching Activities TA/Learning Activities/Evaluation Activities	PDA
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recognize the different types of stress, identifying how each one impacts the ability to cope and emotional management. Replace disturbing thoughts with functional ones and adopt adaptive behaviors in anxious situations through emotional and cognitive self-regulation. Apply strategies to control emotional and behavioral activation to mitigate discomfort and improve coping capacity according to the anxiety situation. <p>Integrate Self-instruction and Self-reinforcement techniques into the training process, strengthening the ability to face stressful situations effectively and proactively.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluate the effectiveness and usefulness of the strategies learned through practical application in real situations, identifying the positive impact on stress management and improvement in coping with academic and personal challenges. 	<p>Activity 1 Recognizing stressful situations in the academic context. (self-study)</p> <p>TA: Microsite Design and Implementation – Activation of coping skills.</p> <p>LA: The student goes through the microsite on foundations about the different types of stress and coping techniques.</p> <p>EA: The student answers the questions associated with each of the thematic sections that are included in the microsite.</p> <p>Activity 2 Role play of coping strategies. (team learning)</p> <p>TA: Design of the different scenarios in coherence with the types of stress in the context of the Faculty of Engineering.</p> <p>Sceneries</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Acute Stress: A student must prepare and present a presentation on a complex topic to a demanding and critical audience within a very tight deadline. The student may experience intense anxiety, pressure, and nervousness due to the importance of the event and the limitation of time to adequately prepare. Sequence Stress: A student experiences sequential stress when, after an intensive week of final exams, she receives news that her academic scholarship is at risk due to her poor performance in a specific subject. This situation adds to the accumulated pressure of exams and places additional stress on her financial and academic situation. <p>Chronic Intermittent Stress: An engineering student working as a research assistant. She faces periods of high work demand during the research project submission season, followed by periods of relative calm. This constant fluctuation between intense periods and less demanding periods contributes to chronic intermittent stress.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Continued Chronic Stress: This type of stress occurs when a student who lives in inadequate and noisy accommodation conditions experiences continued chronic stress. The lack of a quiet and conducive environment for studying affects her concentration and rest, leading to constant and prolonged stress that negatively impacts her well-being and academic performance over time. <p>LA: Students are organized into teams of 3 to 4 members, each of which is assigned one of the designed scenarios.</p> <p>The members of each group act according to the roles that can be presented in the assigned scenario, identifying the emotional reactions that can occur and coping strategies.</p> <p>After the simulation, the group members asked how they managed stress in the scenario and how they could improve in the future.</p> <p>EA: Verification of the recognition of stress according to the case presented. Perception Test.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge Test about types of stress and coping strategies Reflective interview integrates open questions so that participants reflect on their experiences, perceptions, thoughts, and emotions. In the context of coping and self-regulation. <p>Feedback questionnaires:</p> <p>Where students complete after the activity to evaluate their perception of the development of the activity, their understanding of stress and coping strategies, and their self-assessment of their performance.</p>

2.1.2.2 Tools of the Educational Intervention

Three tools are used during the educational intervention, these are: the first is for formal use for the identification of coping skills and is called the Adolescent Coping Scales - ACS, the second and third tools called workshops are built based on the existing information on the characterization of students, special admission programs and integrate specific tools for collecting information; Regarding these, their educational aim and the conceptual support on which they are designed are described.

- The Adolescent Coping Scales (ACS)** Developed by Frydenberg and Lewis (Frydenberg and Lewis 1996b) they are a crucial tool for understanding and evaluating the coping strategies of adolescents, specifically those between 12 and 17 years of age. These scales consist of 79 closed items and one open final item, distributed in 18 subscales. Each item is evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale, reflecting the frequency with which the individual uses a specific coping strategy. The population is 18 students with an average age of 17 years old. One of the most notable aspects of the ACS is its distinction between two versions: one to assess specific coping and another to assess general coping. The specific version allows us to understand

how the adolescent faces situations or problems, while the general version provides a broader vision of how the adolescent faces various situations in his or her daily life. The breadth of subscales on the ACS allows for the exploration of a variety of coping strategies, from problem-focused to emotion-focused approaches. This provides a holistic understanding of adolescent coping skills and can help design effective programs that promote resilience and emotional well-being at this crucial stage of development.

- **Workshop 1 – Coping Skills: Self-Instruction Training:** At the end of the first workshop, the student will be able to implement the Self-Instruction training strategy, which promotes coping skills in cases where there are deficiencies related to cognitive and metacognitive skills that prevent or limit behavior, emotional self-regulation, reflection, analysis, and decision-making to overcome situations satisfactorily.
- **Workshop 2 – Coping Skills: Stress Inoculation Training:** At the end of the first workshop the student will be able to face the situation of presenting to the academic community of the National University of Colombia the results of his research orally, through adequate management of his emotions acquired by their preparation and prior exposure to this type of situation.

2.1.3 Tools for Information Analysis

One of the tools used is ATLAS TI is a qualitative analysis software that allows you to organize, analyze, and visualize textual and multimedia data, facilitating the identification of patterns, themes, and relationships in large data sets. R is a free software and programming environment for the analysis of data statistics and visualization. It offers a wide range of statistical and graphical tools for data processing and the generation of predictive models., Monitoring System is a tool that allows you to supervise activities and providing reports.

3 Conclusions

The implementation of coping strategies contributes to improving the emotional well-being of students by providing them with tools to manage stress, anxiety, and other negative emotions effectively. By learning to deal with difficult situations more effectively, students experience an improvement in their academic performance by reducing the negative effects of anxiety on their ability to concentrate, remember, and make decisions. Coping strategies are useful in academics since they are fundamental life skills. By integrating these strategies into the educational curriculum, students are prepared to face the challenges and demands of everyday life more effectively. Educational intervention that teaches coping strategies contributes to the prevention of mental health problems in students by providing them with tools to manage stress, anxiety, and other emotional difficulties healthily and adaptively. This can have a long-term positive impact on your overall well-being.

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